

UDC: 619:636.2:616.99:576.89:616-084

**PREVENTION OF DICTIOCAULOSIS IN CATTLE
(literature review)**

A.M.Eshkoraev

Email: eskoraevaskad@gmail.com

Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, assistant.

I.Kh.Raimkulov

Email: max.raim0330@gmail.com

Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, assistant.

A.R.Tursunkulov

Email: rustamabduraxmonovich@gmail.com

Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, assistant.

R.A.Rasulov

Email: rustamabduraxmonovich@gmail.com

Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, doctoral student.

Abstract: The scientific article presents epizootological data on dictyocaulosis in cattle, prevention, and the effectiveness of protecting calves from invasion.

Abstract: The scientific article presents epizootological data on dictyocaulosis in cattle, prevention, and the effectiveness of protecting calves from invasion.

Key words: Dictyocaulosis, parasite carriers, pastures, stall-walking, calves.

Relevance of the topic . Dictyocaulosis in ruminants is widespread . The losses caused by dictyocaulosis consist of deaths and forced slaughter of sick animals; young animals that have recovered from the disease develop poorly and are stunted in growth; in adult animals, productivity decreases, and the quality of meat, wool and skin deteriorates. Infested animals are more susceptible to other diseases and suffer more severely from them. Currently, the entire system of measures to combat dictyocaulosis is based on systematic deworming of animals. There is a wide range of anthelmintics on the market, but the vast majority are either toxic or ineffective .

Preventive actions . A sharp increase in the incidence of disease in some areas indicates the presence of a large number of animal carriers of dictyocaul. In farms that are unfavorable with respect to this disease, during the pre-grazing period, especially many calves under the age of one year and a small number of heifer cows are infected. It has been noted that if such animals are not examined and dewormed in

a timely manner before being put out to pasture, they infect areas and watering places with dictyocaulosis, and, consequently, also uninfected calves.

In many farms, calves are dewormed only after the appearance of clinical signs of infestation, when these animals have already released a large number of larvae into the environment, thereby contributing to the reinfection of animals in the herd. It must be remembered that treatment of calves with dictyocaulosis is only effective in the initial stage of the disease and always with double deworming with an interval of 10-12 days. In some cases, other than deworming, no other measures are carried out.

In many zones of the republic, climatic conditions contributed to a significant reduction in the incidence of dictyocaulosis in animals. However, it is not only climatic conditions that explain the decrease in morbidity. In many regions, in order to prevent infection, calves were kept in stalls and ranged. This measure is the most effective in preventing dictyocaulosis.

In this case, calves are raised in isolation and allowed to pasture or kept only in pens. In early spring, camps are set up in dry areas with a well-equipped watering hole away from pastures and other places where older age groups of cattle are kept. Before being transferred to the camps, calves are kept isolated from young animals of the previous year of birth. For grazing, areas are chosen where in the fall there were no young animals or adult animals unaffected by dictyocaulosis. Many farms use areas of sown grass for this purpose.

If there is a sufficient number of pastures, a corral grazing system is organized with periodic changes of areas. Calves free from dictyocaulus are allowed to graze in one area for one to two months, depending on the quality of the grass stand. If the examination reveals animals infected with dictyocaulus, the areas at the beginning of the grazing period are changed every 10-12 days, and with the onset of warm summer days after 5-6 days. Reuse of these areas is allowed no earlier than after 2-3 months.

If there is a lack of grazing, calves are transferred to isolated stall-walk housing. At the same time, in the spring they are grown in a room separate from the dairy farm. For calves to walk, a walking yard is fenced off at a rate of at least 25 m/sq. area for each animal. The pens are equipped with mobile feeders and troughs. The animals are fed with grass cut from areas where cattle infected with dictyocaulosis were not grazed. Calves are watered from clean water bodies. Shade canopies are installed in the yard, and drainage ditches are made around it. The premises and walking yards are kept in proper sanitary condition.

Isolated stall-run keeping of calves, being a good method of preventing dictyocaulosis, also helps to increase productivity and reduce the cost of reared young animals. Many farm managers also report an increase in the average daily weight gain of calves with this method of housing. The improvement of disadvantaged farms from dictyocaulosis requires great attention and constant veterinary supervision over the raising of young cattle. Regardless of the method of keeping calves, 40-45 days after being put on pasture, and then 20-25 days later, it is necessary to carry out diagnostic studies and, if even single dictyocaulus larvae are detected, all animals must be dewormed. Six to seven days after treatment, a follow-up examination should be carried out.

In the fall, calves raised in isolation should be transported to a clean, uncontaminated facility, separated from livestock of other age groups. The next year, animals in this group usually receive isolated young animals of the next year of birth. So, within a few years, the main herd can be completely freed from dictyocaul carriers. But it is necessary to keep in mind the contamination of livestock belonging to citizens. Here it is also necessary to carry out preventive measures.

The introduction of infestations should especially be avoided when calves arrive from other farms. These animals must be kept in quarantine for one month and examined twice for dictyocaulosis and other helminth infections. They can be admitted into the general herd only after complete freedom from helminths. Proper organization of preventive and therapeutic measures against dictyocaulosis will dramatically reduce the incidence and completely improve livestock farms from this invasion.

Conclusions An analysis of domestic and foreign literature indicates that dictyocaulosis in cattle, caused by the nematode *Dictyocaulus viviparus*, is quite widespread. The main role in the epizootology of any helminthiasis belongs to the climatic and geographical conditions of the area, since they determine, firstly, the livestock farming system; secondly, the intensity of accumulation of invasive pathogens in pastures. In December-April there is a decline in EI and AI.

The decrease in invasion during this period is explained by the deworming of animals during the stall period, as well as the self-excretion of nematodes.

Bibliography

1. Ergashov, S. I., & Eshqorayev, A. M. (2023). PROTECTION OF RABBITS FROM EYMERIOSIS (COCCIDIOSIS). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 14(5), 121-127.

2. Ergashov, S. I., & Eshqorayev, A. M. (2023). EMERIOSIS OF RABBITS (LITERATURE ANALYSIS). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 14(5), 114-120.

3. Khushnazarov, A. K., Eshkorayev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT, EPISOTOLOGY, TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF EMERIOSIS IN RABBITS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 65-71.

4. Khushnazarov, A. H., Rayimkulov, I. H., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). СЕМИОПРОФИЛАКСИС ОФ ЕМЕРИОЗИНИНГ ИН РАББИТ. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.

5. Khushnazarov, A., Rayimkulov, I., & Eshkoraev, A. (2023). METHODS OF KEEPING RABBITS IN MODERN CAGES. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.

6. Курбанов, Ш. Х., Отабоев, Х. Э., Эшқораев, А. М., & Фармонов, М. У. (2022). ЖИГАР ТРЕМАТОДАЛАРИНИНГ БИОЭКОЛОГИК ВА ЭПИЗОТОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(9), 256-264.

7. Rayimkulov, I. K., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Kuliev, B. A. (2023). Pathomorphology of Catarrhal-Yiringli Bronchopneumonia in sheep. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 2(2), 43-46.

8. Расулов, У., Хушназаров, А., & Камалов, Ф. (2020). Защитим крупный крот от тейлероизационной болезни. *in Library*, 20(4), 15-16.
9. Турсункулов, А. Р., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2020). ХАЙВОНЛАРНИНГ ЛАРВАЛЬ ЦЕСТОДОЗЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ЧОРАТАДБИРЛАРИ. *ҚОРАКЎЛЧИЛИК ВА ЧЎЛ ЭКОЛОГИЯСИ ИLMИЙ-ТАДҚИҚОТ ИНСТИТУТИ*, 332.
10. Хушназаров, А. Х., Райимкулов, И. Х., Эшқораев, А. М., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). Куён эймериозининг кимёпрофилактикаси. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
11. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Куён эймериозининг тарқалиши ва патологоанатомик ташҳиси. *Library*, 1(1), 15-17.
12. Хушназаров, А., Эшқораев, А., Ахмадалиев, Т., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Эпизоотологические диагностические и профелактические данные эймериоз кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 1068-1080.
13. Хушназаров, А., Райимкулов, И., & Эшқораев, А. (2023). ЗАМОНАВИЙ КАТАКЛАРДА ҚУЁНЛАРНИ БОҚИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.
14. Райимкулов И. Х., Нишанов Д. Х., Жабборов Ф. Ф. КАТАРАЛ-ЙИРИНГЛИ БРОНХОПНЕВМОНИЯНИНГ ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЯСИ (ҚЎЗИЛАРДА) //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 14. – №. 5. – С. 143-148.
15. Хушназаров, А. Х., Райимкулов, И. Х., Эшқораев, А. М., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). Куён эймериозининг кимёпрофилактикаси. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
16. Жабборов, Ф. Ф., Нишанов, Д. Х., & Райимкулов, И. Х. (2023). ҚЎЙ ЭКТОПАРАЗИТЛАРНИНГ КИМЁПРОФИЛАКТИКАСИ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 14(5), 107-113.
17. Raimkulov, I. X., Sattieva, F., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). WE PROTECT POULTRY FROM ECTOPARASITES. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 478-482.
18. Райимкулов, И., & Кулиев-доцент, Б. А. ҚОРАКЎЛ ҚЎЗИЛАРДА КАТАРАЛ-ЙИРИНГЛИ БРОНХОПНЕВМОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИНИНГ ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЯСИ. *ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР АКАДЕМИЯСИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ВЕТЕРИНАРИЯ ВА ЧОРВАЧИЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ҚЎМИТАСИ*, 264.
19. Tursunqulov, A. (2022). QO ‘YLARNING LARVAL SESTODOZLARINI MORFOLOGIYASINI O ‘RGANISH. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 295-297.
20. Rasulovich, T. A., & Isakulovich, T. T. (2022). Analyzing the Epizootology of Sheep Dictyokaulosis and Studying the Effectiveness of Some Anthelmintic Drugs. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE*, 1(6), 22-24.
21. Райимкулов, И., & Кулиев-доцент, Б. А. ҚОРАКЎЛ ҚЎЗИЛАРДА КАТАРАЛ-ЙИРИНГЛИ БРОНХОПНЕВМОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИНИНГ ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЯСИ. *ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА*

МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР АКАДЕМИЯСИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ВЕТЕРИНАРИЯ ВА ЧОРВАЧИЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ҚЎМИТАСИ, 264.

22. Rayimqulov, I. (2023). ЗАМОНАВИЙ КАТАКЛАРДА ҚУЁНЛАРНИ БОҚИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES*.

23. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., Эшқораев, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Химиофилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 56-62.

24. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., & Эшқораев, А. (2023). Способы кормления кроликов в современных клетках. *in Library*, 1(1), 52-57.

25. Rayimkulov, I. K., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Kuliev, B. A. (2023). Pathomorphology of Catarrhal-Yiringli Bronchopneumonia in sheep. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 2(2), 43-46.

26. Rayimkulov, I. X., & Khushnazarova, M. I. (2023). SCIENTIFIC BASIS OF FIGHT AGAINST PARASITIC DISEASES OF AGRICULTURAL ANIMALS.

27. Khushnazarov, A., Rayimkulov, I., & Eshkoraev, A. (2023). METHODS OF KEEPING RABBITS IN MODERN CAGES. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.

28. Райимкулов, И. Х., & Кулиев, Б. А. (2019). Гистохимические показатели при экспериментальной пневмонии у каракульских ягнят.

29. Rayimqulov, I. X., & Xushnazarova, M. I. (2023). QISHLOQ XO 'JALIK HAYVONLARINING PARAZITAR KASALLIKLARGA QARSHI KURASHISHNING ILMIY ASOSLARI.

30. Jabborov, G., & Rayimqulov, I. X. (2022). QO 'Y VA ECHKILARNING EKTOPARAZITLARI VA ULARGA QARSHI DORI VOSITALARINI SINOVDAN O 'TKAZISH. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 86-89.

31. Khushnazarov, A. H., Rayimkulov, I. H., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. V. (2023). СЕМИОПРОФИЛАКСИС ОФ ЕМЕРИОЗИНИНГ ИН РАББИТ. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.

32. Эшқораев, А. М., & Расулов, Р. А. (2024). ЭПИЗООТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ДАННЫЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИЧЕСКИЕ МЕРОПРИЯТИЯ ДИКТИОКАУЛЕЗА КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА (обзор литературы). *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 236-243.

33. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Қуён эймериозининг тарқалиши ва патологоанатомик таҳқиқи. *Library*, 1(1), 15-17.

34. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Распространение и патологоанатомическая диагностика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 15-17.

35. Давлатов, Р., & Хушназаров, А. (2022). Epizootology of eimeriosis (coccidiosis) of rabbits, treatment and preventive measures. *Library*, 22(4), 15.